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A THEMATIC ANALYSIS TO EXPLORE THE CHALLENGES OF EARLY CHILDHOOD CARE AND EDUCATION IN AZAD JAMMU & KASHMIR

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Abstract

The study was planned and executed in Azad Jammu & Kashmir, Pakistan. Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) is one of the most significant educational levels that sets the foundation of human life. Many studies proved that those children who have access to quality early education, have a better understanding of life and are found to be law obeying human beings. This study is planned to identify and explore the challenges of ECCE in Azad Jammu & Kashmir, Pakistan. The study will be an important addition to the existing literature. A qualitative method was adopted. There were school heads, principals, tehsil, and district heads of the educational administration whose interviews were conducted. Additionally, some open-ended questions were asked of respondents during the survey. Sampling was performed in two phases. The study concluded that there are major challenges in infrastructure, curriculum framework, professional teachers, and budget in Azad Jammu & Kashmir. It is recommended that the government of Azad Jammu & Kashmir along with relevant quarters plan to allocate more funds to the ECCE. It is also recommended that the government request international donors and other funding agencies to overcome the overwhelming challenges of infrastructure to provide comfortable and safe shelter to the children. Awareness about child rights may also be published at the state level to sensitize the masses about the significance of child rights.

Keywords: Learning, Education, Childhood, Care, Challenges

Introduction:

Education is one of the significant factors which can play a vital role in the development of any country. It was a significant reason that led to the addition of education in Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs-2015) in section four (4). In these goals, it was stated "To ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning". SDGs focused on Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) in subsection 4.2 as "By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care, and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education". Early learning plays an important role in human life. [Bakken L. et al. \(2017\)](#) concluded that those children who enrolled in early learning programs have a significant difference in social behaviors. [Trawick-Smith \(2014\)](#) reported that children might be more cooperative if they played with equipment that is relevant to their age group in a planned system like a daycare center or early learning institute. [Rasli \(2021\)](#) argued that practitioners, who are part of education need to have soft skills so that they may promote these skills among the children more specifically at early learning centers or schools. These practitioners should have intellectual, emotional, and social skills to impart these to ECE-level students. Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) is accepted as an important level of education in Pakistan. The policy documents reflected ECCE education with different names like Early Childhood Education (ECE) in 2009 educational policy and now it is termed as the ECCE. Moreover, In Pakistan, the [National Education Policy \(2009\)](#) had one chapter on ECE. The government of Pakistan is still working to achieve the mentioned goals in NEP-2009. It is appreciable that policymakers and authorities accepted the significance of Early Childhood Education and Care (ECCE). In Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJ & K), the educational system is

regularly developing. At this time, there are about 8,000 educational institutions ([Azad Kashmir at a Glance 2014](#)) established in the state of AJ & K. There are two categories i.e. 6,000 are government ownership (public) and over 2,000 institutions in the private sector. It is significant to mention, that in 1947 there were 291 schools, in 1977, these were raised to 2085 schools, and in 1988 these institutions were 4567. Data reflected that there is a significant growth in the private sector during the last decade. In Pakistan, [National Educational Policy \(2009 & 2017\)](#), reported no formal pre-primary public schooling. On the same lines, in AJK, there is no formal schooling at the ECCE level in public schools. In AJK, public schools which are about 6000 have no separate teachers for the ECCE education. Most schools are without classrooms and other basic needs. Yet, there is no official commitment at the state level for separate teachers, infrastructure, and separate classrooms for the children of the ECCE classes. However, the private sector is working at ECCE level education in AJK.

Research Problem

Research proved that ECCE is significant for the social and economic development of nations. Individuals who learn in pre-schooling education are more law-obedient, responsible, civilized, and stable personalities ([S.Jawad, et al., 2023](#)). So, ECCE education should be studied and explored. The government of Azad Jammu & Kashmir (Gov. AJK) has the largest Department of Elementary & Secondary Education (DE&SE). This department consists of about 30,000 teachers. This department deals with all levels of education. However, currently there is a dire need to explore the challenges of the ECCE level education in AJK. To find out these challenges, this study is being planned. The study will add a major contribution to future studies at the ECCE level of education, especially in other studies of educational research generally.

Research Objective

- i) To explore, identify, and report the challenges of the ECCE in Azad Jammu & Kashmir.
- ii) To recommend tangible solutions to challenges

Literature Review

Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE)

Every nation has a structure for early childhood education. Childhood education is important for better lives, but it also has significant importance for a nation's future. Early childhood education has different names in the world, which include Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE), Early Childhood Development (ECD), and Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC). However, globally, Early Childhood Development (ECD) is elaborated as "The education for kids, from birth to 8 years of age". According to [UNICEF \(2017\)](#), most ECDs serve from birth to the age of 8 years. At this age, children take an interest in a wide range of activities. Learning in early years (not more than eight years) in human lives is called early childhood education (ECE) ([Siraj-Blatchford et al., 2010](#)). ECE comprises activities that influence children's developmental changes before entering a proper class or primary school. Youngsters do not simply develop physically but are innovative and creative and understand the complexities of life around them. For a youngster to create and learn healthily, it is important to provide fundamental learning about nourishment and human life. It is also important to learn about the essential requirements for communication, encouragement, security, and disclosure in the early years ([National Education Policy, 2009](#)). Learning starts during childbirth. It is concluded in most of the research studies that 80% of the cerebrum is developed in the early years of age, for example, from birth to eight years. ECE impacts all human societies and nations across the globe. It is mostly recognized that

the effects of childhood education and learning at this stage remain long-lasting throughout life ([Ellison et al., 2019](#)). Children learn from their parents how to think. How to respond? And even about the philosophical approaches to life and society as well. The pre-primary teachers taught the kids how a child relates things and learns in school explicitly. The early concern is that a kid constructs all the key components of interest, connectedness, and Enthusiastic knowledge, to be specific certainty, deliberateness, restraint, cooperation, and ability to convey.

Introduction of ECCE

Early childhood Education (ECE) has become a need for policy, programming, and research at both global and national levels, with expanding acknowledgment of the interconnections between the country's objectives and the nature of administrations for every young girl and boy, and their families. At this age, kids take an interest in a wide range of categories of education. A kid's brain is a profoundly incorporated organ, and its various capacities work in a planned manner. A child's wish for prosperity and social fitness gives a solid establishment to developing cognitive abilities ([Desjardins, et al., 2005](#)). The Child's physical and enthusiastic well-being, cognitive-etymological, and social aptitudes, and limits that develop in the early years are critical requirements for school and work. [Uno, K., & Nagai, T. \(2015\)](#) argued that some conditions are very important as the retention of the students depends on the circumstances and environment around the child. Moreover, some researchers claimed that students should have a feasible classroom, loving teachers, and caring environmental conditions to keep them at school. Early childhood educators are specialists, and they must have the desired and required skills to educate, care, nurture, and guide children properly. This reflected that these educators need to make decisions based on data and provide their best efforts

for the growth and development of generations. This field is though needing more focus from communities, policymakers, and educational and political leaders. In the following diagram an overall reflection of the growth of a child. There is a general example of growth that is valid for all kids. Nonetheless, the character and nature of development shifts from kid to youngster (Baker, 2006). ECE alludes not exclusively to what is going on inside the youngster, yet in addition to the consideration, of what a kid requires to flourish. It is a general discernment that before one can fabricate a house, it is essential to establish a framework to help the whole structure. Correspondingly, before a kid enters elementary school, a comparable foundation must be laid, implanted inside their family, their locale, and their cultural values, young youngsters (from birth to eight) need support in their development of the physical, intellectual, passionate, and social capacities that will empower them to endure and flourish in later years. The practical education of the youngster during these long periods of tutoring relies upon an incredible degree upon which the base is laid through the preschool years (National Curriculum on ECE, 2002). Empirical findings from an assortment of orders have exhibited that the help of early development yields rich advantages not just in prompt manners for the youngster and guardians, but after some time as far as the kid's capacity to add to the network. Intercessions in the long early stretches of childhood offer a phenomenal chance to evade or moderate learning problems and to carry enduring advantages to people and society.

Why Is the Ece Necessary?

Alvarado (2012) commented that ECE is a term that alludes to the timeframe from a kid's introduction to the world to when he enters kindergarten. Additionally, she commented that it is a significant time in kids' lives since it is when they initially figure out

how to interface with others, including friends, instructors, and guardians, and start to develop some significant skills that will remain with them for the rest of their lives. In any case, the mentioned scholar said it is a typical misperception that early youth instruction is just about learning essential abilities. At the point when this is done effectively, it lays the basis for it to proceed all through the youngster's training." The primary long periods of life are significant because what happens in early childhood can matter for a lifetime. ECE gives us what youngsters must have and what they should be shielded from to develop their solid advancement. Supporting connections, and responsive, steady, and rich learning encounters in the promptest years give long-lasting advantages to learning, conduct, and physical and mental health. Interestingly, studies about the science of worry in early childhood show how interminable pressure brought about by significant misfortune, for example, extraordinary destitution, misuse, or disregard, can debilitate creating mind engineering and for all time set the body's pressure reaction framework on high alarm, in this way expanding the hazard for a scope of ceaseless sicknesses (Keating, 2010, Vashchenko et al., 2010). Parents play an important role in the education, care, and innovative thoughts of kids. One explanation behind this is that the youngsters whom their parents instruct during their early life education have indistinguishable advantages from kids tried out at the preschool programs, as the kids get special consideration from their parents. Parents should use good language and teach their small kid's inventive thoughts. Kids instructed how to communicate in a second language during their initial creative years are likewise in a situation to learn English at a childhood age (Oren, et al., 2020; Wilson, 2007). Kids were encountering distinctive enhancement as it was additionally indicated that youngsters

with learning or other physical incapacities advantage monstrously from pre-kindergarten education. Moreover, youngsters with parents profoundly associated with their pre-kindergarten education do not encounter similar positive outcomes from Head Start programs as kids originating from homes with no accentuation. Various people do not feel the law-making body should choose if kids should get formal pre-kindergarten training (Marshall, 2018; Warren et al., 2016). Notwithstanding the differentiations in appraisal about formal pre-kindergarten training, kids benefit by getting a type of instruction during their underlying developmental years. While a couple of children benefit hugely from preschool, it may not be the best instructive setting for different adolescents. Kids advantage most by getting instructive direction from their folks. Guardians must survey a child's stand-out character before making sense of which program is generally suitable for a child since not all ventures advantage kids in a comparable way (Eime et al., 2013).

Methodology

Mixed method research was conducted to carry out the objectives. Molina-Azorin (2016) claimed that mixed-method research has been adopted in different fields in recent years. She claimed that this method enabled the researchers to conclude the issue at hand in a better way. Understanding and comprehending the issue or problem with this method is more manageable and comparatively better. This was also reported in the same research that mixed-method research enriches conceptual thinking. This method allows the scholar/researcher to enhance his/her research skills to expand the methodological skills. Creswell (2012) claimed that qualitative data is very convincing to all readers. This data has more words than numbers, which would have a concrete and meaningful interpretation. Furthermore, this type of research provides a

“detailed comprehension of the issue”. This understanding is being developed through communication directly with the most relevant stakeholders. These stakeholders are directly involved in the said issue either in their homes or at the workplace. This qualitative part of the research provided an opportunity to hear the voices of practitioners. After studying the above recent researchers, the scholar decided to proceed with a mixed-method study. This study has used both quantitative and qualitative methods. A survey was conducted. Meanwhile, interviews and open-ended questions were asked from the respondents. This is the reason that instrument development, data collection, and words are explained in two sections i.e. quantitative and qualitative parts.

Population

The population of the study is presented in the following table. The population may be divided into the following three different sets: The focus of the study was educational stakeholders within Azad Jammu & Kashmir. All the primary, middle, high, and higher secondary schools, along with their teachers, were the population of the study.

- All the teachers (Primary section only).
- Educational leadership social sciences.

Sampling:

Sampling has been done in two steps. In the first step, a stratified sampling technique was used. Three strata have been found in the State of Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK), which are Muzaffarabad, Poonch, and Mirpur. These three divisions were declared as civil divisions of the AJK, which have different geographical locations as well. So, one district from each division has been picked based on literacy rate. The literacy report of Alif Ailaan District Ranking 2017 was the reference. One district from the top (highest literacy rate), one from the middle, and one from the bottom (least literacy) were selected. Three administrative divisions have equal representation in the

sample. All these three have one district in the selected sample as represented in red color in the 3.1 map. However, in the second step, schools have been selected based on their status either public or private schools (Only primary sections) from each district. This is worth mentioning that, during this step, a simple random technique is used to select the schools.

Data Collection

Teachers, principals, AEOs, and DEOs as well as staff from secretariat education, participated in the study. This paper is particularly related to the open end as well as in-depth interviews of the teachers, principals, AEOs, DEOs, and directors from the secretariat. Teachers and principals responded to questionnaires' and filled in the open-ended part. So, the data extracted from open-ended questionnaires as well and themes were developed.

Data Analysis:

Collected data entered in the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). Data was analyzed concerning the research objectives. Thematic analysis is being applied considering [Braun & Clarke's \(2006\)](#) guide. This guide recommends the scholar apply six steps in thematic analysis. The first step was to read and re-read the collected data. During this process, it was mentioned that the scholar needed to develop the notes of ideas, which were found in the data set ([Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 87](#)). To complete this task, the researcher listened to the recorded interview again and again. Along with the interview, the collected answers to open-ended questions were also read, re-read, and transcribed into main ideas. Through this repeated process, major ideas, repeated words, and areas were noted down. The **second step** as recommended, was "generating the initial codes". During this step, Braun and Clarke recommended coding the interesting points of the data logically in the entire data set. In this step, the data was

reduced. During **step three**, one had to find out the themes. So, the scholar did the same. After gathering all the data, potential themes were extracted. **Step four** reflected the procedure where one must check out the themes. During checking of themes, it had to be observed that either theme worked concerning the codes (level 1) and with whole data (level 2). This process led to the map analysis. At this step, reviewing the themes at step three was carried out in two levels. At the first level, all the codes of themes were read and identified, if there was any coherent pattern being developed. However, for the second level, another critical reading was done in the whole data set, to observe that themes fit concerning the data. This process, importantly, was helpful to explore if any data was missed during coding. In **step five**, in this phase, one had to define and name the themes. In this step, the naming of themes is most important through the definition of these themes. The major objective of this level was to define each theme precisely. Therefore, during this study, the scholar defined each theme during this process and identified under which objective and research question these themes fit. **Step Six**, Reporting the results: the conclusion of all drilling practiced above. Reporting the results, linking these results with objectives/research questions/hypothesis and literature review. During this step, the scholar analyzed and interpreted the data in a narrative form. This provided the scholar with an opportunity to write precise, accurate, concrete, logical, and authentic arguments within data and among themes.

Findings:

Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis was performed on collected data. There had been different themes which were extracted from the collected data. Both respondents' i.e. teachers and principals filled out open-ended questionnaires. However, in-depth

interviews were conducted with District Education Officers (DEOs), Assistant Education Officers (AEOs), the President of a Private School Organization, and a representative of the education department, nominated by the Secretary Department of Elementary and Secondary Education, Government of Azad Jammu & Kashmir.

Challenges to Early Childhood Care and Education:

Budget:

A major challenge regarding the ECCE, in the State of AJK, is identified as the availability of funds. Currently, the Department of Elementary and Secondary Education is one of the major departments among 27 government departments concerning human resources and budget. According to reports (AJK at a glance-2016), about 29000 teachers were working in this department. Despite these statistics, the government did not plan to launch a comprehensive ECCE program in public schools. The representative of the Department said that funds are not sufficient at present to implement this program on a large scale. The government supported a few projects regarding the establishment of ideal classrooms at pilot high schools in each district in the first phase. These projects are funded by international donors and NGOs. Most of the funds are allocated to operational costs rather than the development budget, so the government is unable to facilitate public schools with modern facilities. After the devastating disaster of the earthquake of 2005, it was expected that most of the primary schools would be built by the latest needs; however, it could not be done. A project, funded by the Asian Development Bank (ADB) to construct some selected primary schools, has been implemented successfully. Some of the primary schools or primary sections of the high or middle schools are yet to be facilitated with basic needs. GoAJK must make education the priority. The quantitative data also reflected that

practitioners who are working at the ECCE level are demanding more budgets for THE ECCE, irrespective of the private or public sector. The government can request international donors to help them provide future generations with a better infrastructure at the school level.

Trained Teachers

Another major challenge, which emerged during the interviews of government representatives and from open-ended questions, is that trained Montessori teachers are not available. It was also explored that there were no separate slots for the ECCE, available in public schools or the Department of Elementary and Secondary School, Gov. AJK. The question about the trained teachers probes the educational leaders and how they are looking into it. One DEO argued "We do not have any prescribed criteria to hire the specialized teachers of the ECCE in public schools. It is good that private schools have policies to recruit teachers in early grades. I know some schools that hire specialized teachers to teach at the ECCE. He further added that public schools have rules to hire the services of those graduates who have done B.Ed. Now the question about the ECCE training is important. There are no rules to hire those trained people who have certifications for the ECCE from accredited institutions. Henceforth, it can be concluded that there is no space for such teachers in the department." Another interviewee commented, "ECCE level of education needs some political and social pressure so that it emerges in a public school in true spirit. For this, there is a need for lobbying within the department and outside the department to allocate the slots for ECCE education. Montessori certifications are significant for our teachers who are working at ECCE, unfortunately at times there are no options for such trained human resources." Additionally, another AEO concluded her interview with these words "Montessori

teacher's training is not important for the services of teachers in E & SE department. The department welcomes the traditional teacher's training programs like B.Ed. and M.Ed. This leads to the demotivation of certifications, which promote the required skills of teachers at the ECCE level. Nowadays, there are new concepts like multi-grade teaching and multi-subject teaching. Though our primary school's teachers are using all these pedagogical approaches unfortunately these approaches are not learned from any professional development course." A principal from private schools argued, "We used to conduct the teacher's training on campus. Additionally, we as a school prefer to hire those teachers who have Montessori certifications." In the above discussion of DEO, it was found that private schools are hiring professional teachers. On the other hand, in public sector schools, efforts are needed to set a standardized way forward for recruitment of the ECCE teachers. There may be strong lobbying and sensitization needed for the recruitment of such teachers at the ECCE. Separate and complete guidelines are needed to hire trained teachers.

Child Rights

Children are the future of any nation. During the school visits, it is observed that child rights are not drafted. Teachers and school administrators deal with the children the way they think is best and most suitable. Some of them even believed in corporal punishment. Their rights are most important in any state. During the data collection and analysis, this theme was also extracted. A principal in a private school explained his situation "Parents sometimes pressure the teachers and principal to punish students. These motivations lead to corporal punishment. Later, when we asked the teacher about her act, she claimed that her parents asked me to do this if the child was not following the instructions. We are arranging different training and professional development for

teachers to change their beliefs and approaches. Meanwhile, schools are trying to educate the parents about how to deal with the children at their home places." A DEO argued during the interview "Our parents need more awareness to deal with the children at their home places along with teachers. Teachers are also lacking in this area. Traditionally we people are dealing with the children with routine behaviors and calling them with different names. Such names shook the confidence of students. Students should be dealt with care. However, teachers did not accept this approach as much as it demanded. This leads to creating a challenging situation to handle such issues at school premises. Importantly, we need to create a social environment to deal with the children with respect and love." Representative of Gov. AJK commented, "A draft of child's rights proposed in the legislative assembly which, most probably, would be passed from the assembly. Department of Elementary and Secondary Education (DE & SE) is planning to launch an awareness campaign among all the stakeholders. This will play a significant role in promoting a lively environment for the children in different social quarters of the society." Child rights need more attention. Children may be dealt with due respect, care, and love. There should not be any corporal punishment at school sites. All the relevant stakeholders should plan to promote a lovely environment for children to promote holistic development among children.

Curriculum

Presently, there are no guidelines about the curriculum for both sectors of early childhood care and education. National Curriculum for early childhood education has been declared and announced but Azad Jammu & Kashmir Assembly did not adopt that document. Due to this, there are no guidelines and standards at the ECCE level of education. This is an important challenge in hand to deal with due

attention. Government schools are also teaching some private publishers' books without any guidance. About this important issue, the government representative argued, "Government is developing the curriculum for early childhood care and education." One of the major areas and guidelines for early practitioners is curriculum framework and guidelines. An early educator from the private sector claimed, "At present, we do not have any curriculum guidelines from Gov. AJK. We also develop the syllabus for the early education level ourselves. During our legal requirements, we just need to share the publisher's name, rather than share the whole document with the department of E & SE." Another teacher commented, "We plan our yearly teaching topics and contents. We share this with the parents of the students and execute the idea as per plan. There were no official guidelines from the Department of E & SE, provided. However, a comprehensive discussion from our supervisor/principal is being arranged when we submit our plans." A public sector teacher argued, "The Department notified the publishers' names so that we can guide the parents. These books are available in the market. There are no more details about the annual plan, play days, outdoor activities, national day celebrations, or anything more about the curriculum. We do not have any play facilities or budget to organize these activities in the school." The curriculum framework is an integral part of the policy development. After policy guidelines, curriculum guidelines should be available to all the stakeholders of the ECCE. At times, DE & SE (Gov. AJK) is lacking in this area.

Support to the Private Sector

The data showed that the private sector is also working at ECCE level. The quantitative section of this research concluded that teacher's practices in private schools are better than in public schools. Currently, there are private schools that are providing the

ECCE services to the masses. These schools or daycare centers are registered with DE & SE. Unfortunately, the exact number of schools working in AJK is missing. During the interview with a DEO, she concluded, "Private sector has better infrastructure at ECCE level like classrooms, drinking water, electricity, and playground. Likewise, these schools are charging more fees to parents but providing a better ECCE-level education. These schools have trained teachers. We as DE & SE are not supporting these private schools." A teacher from a private school wrote, "Though we are educating the children, however we are not eligible for any public funding" Another principal from a private school wrote, "I am not sure, why the government is not considering our services and offering any kind of competitive grant to private sector. Alif Elaan's report raised the issues of infrastructure in AJK, but in the private sector we are offering all the required basic infrastructure and facilities." An Assistant Education Officer (AEO) argued that the "Private sector has a better approach to fix the day-to-day issues as they do not have time taking procedures to get financial approvals. Additionally, infrastructural facilities are also better in these private schools along with instructional facilities. However, we do not have any option to support these schools so that they can improve." The government should plan to support these schools so that they can offer better services for ECCE students. This is an important issue and needs to be addressed.

Infrastructure

The data showed many concerns about the infrastructure. Earlier reports ([Alif Elaan 2016](#), [UNICEF 2016](#)) in AJK also raised serious concerns about the infrastructure of these schools. During data collection, researchers found that primary schools usually have one room or maybe two rooms. These schools consisted of at least five classes and maybe six in some public primary schools. Despite all

this, there are fewer washrooms and sometimes no washrooms at school, especially at public schools. Availability of playground, drinking water, no helper (peon) or Aya at school to support the ECCE children for toileting, and sitting arrangement of students are serious concerns in these public schools. A head teacher commented "We used to write regularly to our administration about these issues. No one responds to us or hears about our issues. These are serious concerns. We try to involve the community in the settlement of these issues but unfortunately, people have other questions like the availability of teachers after settling the infrastructure issues. I am not able to make such commitments" Furthermore, she concluded "We do not have any funds to fix our issues. We came to know that there are no funds for schools to develop classrooms or fix other issues in our schools. These are serious concerns, and we need to think about it." In high schools, comparatively, the situation is better. One of the headmasters argued "We do have classrooms, playgrounds, water facility, washrooms, and sports equipment for the students. Though comfortable chairs decorated and furnished classrooms are needed at the time. We are hopeful that soon we will offer these facilities at our school. At our school, we do have a proper place and our children are quite safe." On the contrary, private schools usually have required classrooms. However, space issues are there in both private and public schools. Teachers reported about this issue in the open-ended questions along with schools' heads. However, private sector teachers and principals shared that the government did not support them with land acquisition and infrastructure like buildings, etc.

Conclusion

The study concluded that the annual budget, trained human resources, infrastructure, support to the private sector, and child rights are major challenges of ECCE in AJK. These

challenges need a strong political and departmental commitment to be addressed. Moreover, the private sector is working in this sector. This sector needs some projects from the government. When the government announces some competitive process to facilitate these institutions, then definitely the quality of services may be better. Children need more comprehensive and quality services with safety. The influence and monitoring of government will play a significant role in the promotion of ECCE services and overcoming these challenges. There is also a need to involve civil society and parents, so that these challenges may be addressed regularly.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommended that:

- The government may allocate a budget for ECCE level of education.
- There may be the promotion of institutions that provide pre-and in-service teacher training to ECCE teachers.
- There is a dire need to find ways to overcome the infrastructure issues of ECCE classes.
- Government and private service providers may seek help from donors and NGOs to provide better services for children.
- Awareness campaigns may be launched about child rights among the masses from early service providers.
- Political leadership may devise some rules and regulations to promote child rights.

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